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Effects of Sow Parity on Reproductive and Progeny Performance in a Yorkshire Farrow-to-Finish Sow herd

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Abstract

Reproductive performance data from maternal line Yorkshire sow herd (n=103) sows were collected from the Swine Research & Education Center, Auburn University, Auburn, Alabama to determine if prior reproductive experience and/or sow parity had a beneficial effect on reproductive competence. Overall reproductive performance values recorded were 83.7 ± 21.5% for farrowing rate, 12.8 ± 3.3 for number born, 10.7 ± 2.9 for number born alive, 8.8 ± 2.0 for number weaned, 1.5 ± 0.3 kg for individual piglet birth weight, 8.4 ± 1.6 kg for weaning weight, 8.06 ± 3.0 days for wean-to-estrus interval, 17.9 ± 2.0 mm for pre-farrowing backfat depth and 14.2 ± 1.5 mm for post farrowing backfat depth respectively respectively. Farrowing rate was lowest in first parity sows (72.6%) and highest in parity 5 sows (95.8%). Parity effects were highly significant ($P < 0.01$) for total number born (11.46±3.0, 12.46 ±3.4, 15.57±2.1, 14.92±2.9, 13.40 ±3.0, 11.67±1.3, 11.40±4.3, 10.25±2.5) and number born alive (9.50±2.3, 10.92±3.6, 12.29±1.5, 12.58±2.7, 11.30±2, 10.67±1.3, 9.00±3.0, 8.75±2.3) for parities 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8+ respectively. Number born alive was lower in litters from sows in parities ≥7 than those in parities 2-5, but was not different when compared to the other parities. Average piglet weight at birth (ABW) and weaning, and number of piglets (NW) weaned were not significantly ($P > 0.05$) influenced by sow parity. Average birth weight was lightest in PG 1 sows and was highest in PG 2 and PG 3 sows. The results from the present study suggest a significant drop in reproductive performance, progeny performance, and survivability of progeny between PG 1 sows and mature sows that are retained in the herd. It is recommended that sows should be maintained in the herd for additional parities as long as the sows reproduce regularly and wean large litters. By maintaining a parity structure that retains more mature sows, the system allows sows to reach peak perform, maximize reproductive performance, and throughput across the breeding herd.

Keywords: Reproductive performance, parity, Yorkshire, sows

INTRODUCTION

Around 19% of the reproductive sows in a herd are primiparous sows, i.e. sows after first weaning (Hoge and Bates, 2011). Their reproductive performance, i.e. farrowing rate and litter size, has a large impact on farm productivity. In general, reproductive performance is supposed to increase with increasing parity, reaching the highest level from parity 3 to 5 (Koketsu et al. 2017; Hughes and Varley, 2003). Many sows, however, show an equal or lower litter size in second parity than in first parity (Morrow et al., 1992; Saito et al., 2010). This negatively influences reproductive efficiency of second parity sows and thereby farm productivity (Willis et al., 2003). Since reproductive failure is one of the main reasons for culling in young sows (Lucia et al., 2000), improving primiparous sows' reproductive performance might also increase sow longevity and thereby decrease replacement costs. Furthermore, second parity reproductive performance might also be related to subsequent reproductive performance; however, little information is available on this relation.

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Litter size and farrowing rate are important determinants of sow reproductive performance and farm reproductive efficiency. Both farrowing rate and litter size usually increases as parity increases, reaching the highest levels from parity 3 to 5 (Koketsu, 2003; Hughes and Varley, 2003). However, early parity sows (primiparous), i.e. sows of which their first litter is weaned, frequently show an equal or smaller litter size compared with the litter size in first parity sows (Hoving et al., 2011). Besides an equal or smaller litter size, a reduced farrowing rate or a high percentage of sows returning into estrus after insemination can be indicative of suboptimal reproduction in early parity sows. Suboptimal reproductive performance in early parity sows negatively affects their reproductive performance, but it has also been relation to reproductive performance in subsequent parities and to earlier culling of sows (Hoving et al., 2011). Voluntarily culling sows prior to parity 5 or 6 limits the productivity of the system by culling sows prior to reaching peak performance and replacing them with gilts that have significantly poorer reproductive performance, reduced progeny performance, and progeny with reduced odds of surviving to market.

There is balance between genetic progress and system productivity that needs to be evaluated within each system. By maintaining a parity structure that retains mature sows, a system allows sows to reach peak perform. Retaining mature sows also provides the system with an opportunity to reduce the initial investment in replacement gilts, maximize reproductive performance, and maximize throughput across an entire system. Identifying maternal lines with the genetic capacity to remain in the herd, reach peak performance, and maximize a system's performance remains a critical decision for every system. The results from several studies have indicated that there is a significant drop in reproductive performance, progeny performance, and survivability of progeny between parity 1 sows and mature sows that are retained in the herd. Aged sows also have lower reproductive performance than parities 2–5 sows. There are various reasons for this lower performance. For example, ovulation and fertilization rates decrease in aged sows. In addition, they tend to have increased embryonic mortality or pregnancy loss, and more stillborn piglets due to slower responses to the space demands by growing fetuses and to the stimuli from parturition processes (Okere, 1994).

Yorkshire (Large White) pigs are white in color and have erect ears. They are the most recorded breed of swine in the United States and Canada. They are found in almost every state, with the highest populations being in Illinois, Indiana, Iowa, Nebraska and Ohio. The modern Yorkshire is very muscular, with a high proportion of lean meat and low backfat, in addition to being very sound and durable. The Yorkshire breed was developed in England in the county of York. Later, the name was changed to "English Large White" but it is known as Yorkshire throughout most of the rest of the world. There are three types of hogs referred to as the Yorkshire: the large, the middle and the small types. Only the large type has ever gained any prominence in the United States. Today, Yorkshires are productive, yet more performance oriented and more durable than ever. The goal of the Yorkshire breed is to be a source of durable mother lines that can contribute to longevity and carcass merit. (NSR, 2018).

Objectives of this study were to compare lifetime sow and progeny performance across parities in maternal line Yorkshire swine herd, and to determine the optimum number of parities for a sow in a farrow to finish breeding system to maximize returns over total costs per weaned pig and net return on investment. The results presented in this study will provide swine producers with methods of enhancing sow longevity, making educated culling and selection decisions for their farms as well as a means to select superior dams early in their life that can potentially lead to increases in herd profitability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Project location

Reproductive performance data from sows that farrowed between 2016 and 2017 were collected from the Swine Research & Education Center, Auburn University, Auburn, Alabama, U.S.A. This facility is a

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confinement farrow-to-finish operation utilizing a mixture of artificial insemination and natural mating involving crossbred and purebred boars mated to purebred maternal line Yorkshire gilts/sows.

Animal Management

Both gilts and weaned sows, sows were housed in the breeding barn and housed in groups of six in a 10.0 x 4.0 –m pens with partial slatted floor. Females were checked for estrus twice a day using a mature boar. On the first day of standing estrus, females were hand mated or were inseminated using a commercial AI dose. A second insemination took place when the standing estrus extended to the next day. An ultrasound pregnancy check was done 4 weeks after insemination. Parity records (n = 103) from F1 Yorkshire females which farrowed from January 2016 through September 2017 were used to evaluate differences in reproductive performance by parity. The average parity of sows in the study was 3.4 ± 2.0 , but ranged from parity 1 through parity 11 with an average lactation length of 19.0 ± 2.3 days. For the purposes of this study, sows of parities ≥ 8 were combined into one parity class. Performance among parities ≥ 8 were not significantly different from each other and combining parities provided a more equal distribution of number of sows within parity categories. Actual feed intake per sow or gilt was not recorded. During the weaning to insemination interval, sows were individually housed in crates and were fed a commercial gestation diet with a maximum of 3.5 kg of per day. During pregnancy, sows were housed in individual gestation stalls. Sows were fed a commercial gestation diet. Feeding level on farm A was 2.5 kg per day for the first 60 days of gestation, 2.8 kg per day from days 61 to 85, and 3.4 kg per day from day 86 for the remaining gestation.

Data Collection

Parity differences were estimated for number born alive (NBA), total born (TB), number of pigs nursed after transfer (NAT), average piglet birth weight (ABW), number of pigs weaned (NW), 21-day litter weaning weight (LWW), and wean-to-service interval (WTSI). Prior to evaluation, LWW was adjusted to a 21-day LL and to a LS of 12 pigs nursed. Within 24 hours of birth, piglets were individually weighed, identified, and piglets were cross-fostered to balance litters for number of piglets nursed. Number born alive (NBA) was recorded as the number of piglets born alive within each litter. Number after transfer (NAT) was recorded as the number of piglets nursing after cross-fostering occurred. As part of management protocol on the farm, more piglets were placed on parity 1 sows in an effort to stimulate mammary development. Number weaned (NW) was recorded as the number of piglets weaned in that litter during the weaning process. Piglets that were born alive were included in the analysis and parity was recorded as the sow's parity at the time of farrowing. No records were kept of individual piglet cross-fostering nor if a piglet was moved to a sow with a different parity of sow born from.

Body weight was recorded on the day of breeding and weaning. BF depth was measured with an ultrasonic probe (Renco Corp, Minneapolis, MN) approximately 4 cm lateral to the dorsal midline at the shoulder (P1), last rib (P2) and last lumbar vertebra (P3). Loin muscle depth was measured at the last rib. BCS were determined by visual appraisal of body condition (1 to 3; 1 = thin, 2 = moderate, 3 = fat). Rebreeding traits included first day of breeding after weaning and percent bred by 10 day after weaning. In this study, animals representing 5 parities were included. However, parity was split into three levels. First parity animals were entered as level one, parity 2-3 sows were entered as level 2, and older sows ($>$ parity 4) were assumed as a level three. WEI was the number of days of days from weaning to the first day of estrus, which also corresponded to the first day of breeding.

Data Analysis

The studied variables for reproductive performance are the interval from weaning to estrus (WEI), the interval from weaning to conception (WCI), which was defined as the number of days between weaning and successful insemination; the farrowing rate (FR), which is defined as the proportion of inseminated sows that

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farrowed related to the total number of inseminated sows (including gilts and sows that were culled before successful farrowing) and the subsequent FR. Prior to evaluation, LWW was adjusted to a 21-day LL and to a LS of 12 pigs nursed. The effects of parity on selected reproductive performance parameters were determined utilizing a one-way analysis of variance procedure (ANOVA) *Statistix 7*, 2000 (Analytical Software, Tallahassee, FL). Initial analysis included parity as a fixed effect; however, due to limited observations and no significant statistical differences ($P > 0.05$) in reproductive performance beyond parity 8 the final model included 8 categories for the effect of parity: PG 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and ≥ 8 . Differences were evaluated by comparing by least squares means between each parity group.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Mean values for all variables recorded across parities are presented in Table 4. Overall values recorded included $83.7 \pm 21.5\%$ for FR, 12.8 ± 3.3 for TB, 10.7 ± 2.9 for NBA, 8.8 ± 2.0 for NW, 1.5 ± 0.3 kg for individual piglet birth weight, 8.4 ± 1.6 kg for WW, 17.9 ± 2.0 mm for pre-farrowing backfat depth, 14.2 ± 1.5 mm for post farrowing backfat depth respectively, 230.2 ± 35.0 kg for sow weaning weight and 8.06 ± 3.0 days for WEI respectively. Taken together, the weaning weight and fat depth results indicate that sows mobilize fat and become leaner the longer they remain in the herd. In the present study, significant differences in reproductive performance, progeny performance, and progeny survival were estimated between each parity group. Least squares means for overall reproductive performance are presented in Table 1.

Farrowing rate (FR) was inconsistent throughout P1-P8. FR in P1 was significantly lower than P5, being almost 24% lower than P5. FR was lowest in first parity sows (72.6%) and highest in parity 5 (95.8%). For other parities, FR was not significantly different ($P < 0.05$; Table 6). Litter size and FR are important determinants of sow reproductive performance in addition to herd reproductive efficiency. Both FR and LS usually increase as parity increases, reaching the highest levels from parity 3 to 5 (Koketsu et al., 2017; Hughes and Varley, 2003). However, second parity sows, i.e. sows of which their first litter is weaned, frequently show a lower FR and smaller LS compared with their LS in first parity. Besides an equal or smaller LS, a reduced FR or a high percentage of sows returning into estrus after insemination can also be indicative of suboptimal reproduction in primiparous sows. Suboptimal reproduction in second parity sows negatively affects second parity reproductive performance, but it has also been related to a reduced reproductive performance in subsequent parities and to earlier culling of sows. Gilts typically exhibit a 10 to 15% lower farrowing rate than multiparous sows. Primiparous sows also have a 3 to 5% lower farrowing rate than multiparous sows.

Farrowing rate remains relatively constant from P2 through P5 or more, and then begins to decrease significantly around P7 or P8. The lower FR of gilts and primiparous sows may be due to the presence of more sub-fertile females in these groups than in higher-parity groups, in which subpar females have already been culled. However, bred P1 sows that return to estrus and require a repeat breeding do not seem to have a higher rate of recurrence of repeat breeding at the P2 and P3 level than P1 sows that do not require a repeat breeding. Litters that result from a repeat breeding tend to be about 0.5 pigs larger than litters that result from no repeat breeding.

These findings add support to the argument that P1 sows that fail to conceive or remain pregnant should get at least one more chance. Farrowing failure or return to service commonly occurs in commercial breeding herds, with approximately 10% of female pigs that fail to farrow being reserved. It has been shown that FR decreases by at least 10% with each reservice (Koketsu, 2003). Returned females tend to have estrous behavior that is different from non-returned females. These behavioral differences include having short estrus duration or weak estrus signs, both of which are hard to detect when determining appropriate timing of inseminations. Analysis of 114,906 females found that 38% had one or more returns in lifetime (Tani et al., 2016). Any such occurrence increases non-productive days of female pigs and decreases their productivity. In the study, 33% of

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the first-returned females had a second return in the same or later parity. In particular, 41% of first-returned gilts had a second return. So, females having a return-to-service are at risk for having another return and these returned females should be closely monitored.

As shown in Tables 2 and 3, parity effects were highly significant ($P < 0.01$) for TB (11.46 \pm 3.0, 12.46 \pm 3.4, 15.57 \pm 2.1, 14.92 \pm 2.9, 13.40 \pm 3.0, 11.67 \pm 1.3, 11.40 \pm 4.3, 10.25 \pm 2.5) and NBA (9.50 \pm 2.3, 10.92 \pm 3.6, 12.29 \pm 1.5, 12.58 \pm 2.7, 11.30 \pm 2, 10.67 \pm 1.3, 9.00 \pm 3.0, 8.75 \pm 2.3) for parities 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8+ respectively. NBA was lower in litters from sows in parities ≥ 7 than those in parities 2-5, but was not different when compared to the other parities. Milligan et al. (2002b) reported number born alive was highest in parity 3-5 ($P < 0.05$). Strang (1970) found that number of piglets born alive is lowest in the first litter, increases sharply to a maximum parity 4 and 5 litters and then declines gradually in later litters. Quiniou et al. (2002) reported that, prolificacy decreased in older sows above parity 4. Parity 1 and 2 females weaned more piglets than females in parity 3-6 and ³ 8. NW was not different in parities 5 and higher. Moeller et al., (2004) found number weaned to be numerically higher in parity 3-5 females compared to all other parities. Strang (1970) examined parity differences from 38,000 Yorkshire litters to investigate variation affecting litter productivity. Results from this study showed that NBA increased progressively with parity up to the fourth litter and then declined gradually as parity increased. Number of piglets at weaning was found to be the highest at parity three and gradually decrease as sows became older. This was affected by the mortality from birth to three weeks of age, which was found to be the lowest at parity one litters and then increase progressively with increasing parity. Litter weight and average piglet weight at 3 weeks of age was found to be highest at parity 3 and 2, respectively.

Similar results were obtained by Krahn (2015) who found that the number weaned per litter were higher from parity 1-3 compared to all other parities. The number of piglets weaned per litter decreased as parity increased with females in parity 6 and greater having the lowest number of piglets weaned per litter. The results of this study differ from Milligan et al., (2002b) who reported, number weaned was highest in parities 3-5. Additional piglets were placed on parity 1 and 2 sows during the cross-fostering period, which may explain more piglets weaned per litter in these parities. According to Krahn (2015), litters from parity 3-5 females had the higher NBA compared to parities 1-2 and ≥ 8 females. Litters from females in parity 1 and 8 and greater, had lower NBA compared to those in parity 2-6 females. Moeller et al. (2004) confirmed similar findings to this study in which NBA was significantly highest in parity 3-5 compared to all other parities.

Yoder et al. (2014) showed that the NBA and TB were smallest in first parity sows and steadily increased through PG 5 and then slowly started to decline. Twenty-one-day litter weaning weight was also significantly lower in PG 1 sows, and was nearly 15 pounds heavier in PG 2 sows and over 10 pounds heavier in PG 5 sows. WTSI was highest in PG 1 sows and significantly decreased as PG increased. The reduction in WTSI of nearly two days between PG 1 and PG 2 sows was the largest change and once sows reach PG 3 or older, WTSI was up to 3.5 days shorter than it was in PG 1 sows, reducing farrowing interval and maximizing litters/sow/year. Sows are continually maturing throughout their productive life and do not reach mature size until parity 6 thus it makes sense that as sows continue to mature their productivity continues to increase and peak performance will occur later in a sow's lifetime. Number weaned was higher in the first 3 PGs, but was a function of the farm's cross-fostering program which allotted more pigs to be fostered to younger sows (PG1 through PG4) than older animals. The ability of sows in the population used in this study to wean a high number of pigs is consistent throughout a sow's lifetime, but is highly dependent on the number pigs the sow is allowed to nurse.

The relation between LS in first and second parity and LS in later parities can be due to genetic differences in reproductive potential, but can also be due to (genetic) differences in the ability to cope with a suboptimal environment. For example, Bloemhof et al. (2013) reported differences in heat stress tolerance, measured by reproductive performance, between two sow lines. In practice this might mean that some sows are able to maintain a sufficiently high feed intake during high environmental temperatures in the farrowing room, whilst others are not. As a result, weight loss of the former sows might be lower and their

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reproductive performance higher than the latter sows. Optimal farm management based on individual sows, however, might reduce differences between sows, as is illustrated by the high correlation ($r = 0.91$, $P < 0.0001$) between first and second parity litter size on many farms (Hoving et al. 2011). Furthermore, the effect of first parity litter size on subsequent reproductive performance might also be due to the long-lasting effects of gilt management on sow development (Challinor et al., 1996; Tummaruk et al., 2001a). Gilt rearing and gilt breeding strategies determine, for a large part, first parity litter size but also determine sow body development and thereby the ability of a gilt to withstand weight losses during first lactation. The NBA in a litter was not significantly correlated with parity while the number weaned indicates a very slight negative correlation with parity (Khran, 2015).

Average piglet weight at birth (ABW) and weaning weight (WW), and number of piglets weaned (NW) were not significantly ($P > 0.05$) influenced by sow parity (Tables 5 and 6). ABW was lightest in PG 1 sows and was highest in PG 2 and PG 3 sows. There was a slight reduction in ABW as sows continued to mature, but ABW was still significantly higher than PG 1 sows in each PG through PG 8 (Yoder et al 2014). Mean birth weight was not significantly correlated with parity. This could be due to the lower mean birth weight in parities 1 and ≥ 7 females compared to parity 2-4 females (Krahn, 2015).

Piglet birth weight is vital to future performance of that pig and a reduction in individual piglet birth weight has been associated with poorer pig quality, higher mortality rates, fewer full value pigs at market, fatter, and lighter muscled pigs at market. Retaining mature sows should significantly boost reproductive performance and produce more quality pigs for a system. Birth or weaning weight and preweaning growth rate indicate the quality of piglets, and positively affect their post weaning growth performance. Increased colostrum intake reduces piglet mortality, and increases preweaning and post weaning growth performance (Declerck, 2016). In addition, higher preweaning growth in piglets is associated with higher post weaning growth performance (Wolter, 2001). The preweaning growth rate can be increased by management tools such as the use of a milk replacer and two-step nursing (Douglas, 2014). The birth weight and preweaning growth rate of piglets that will become replacement gilts are characteristics of litter-of-origin for subsequent reproductive performance of sows in later life (Bruun, 2016). Higher preweaning growth in replacement gilts is associated with a lower age at puberty. These characteristics appear to affect the subsequent reproductive performance of sows. Lower birth weight is associated with more NBA in the litter, whereas weaning weight and preweaning growth are affected by sow milk production and producers' lactational management. Therefore, extremely light gilts born to sows that farrowed large NBA should not be selected as replacement gilts. Furthermore, increased preweaning growth is critical to improve subsequent sow performance in later life.

Roehe and Kalm (2000) estimated the genetic and environmental risk factors associated with pre-weaning mortality in piglets using generalized linear mixed models. Records from 12,727 piglets born alive from 1338 litters were used to predict the odds ratios of parity differences. An increase in parity showed to have higher odds of mortality for piglets until weaning. This may be closely related with the increase in number born, as well as the increase in variation within a litter which has a tendency for a higher mortality. This was also reported by Fix et al. (2010b) in which a significant negative correlation was found with an increase in parity and pre-weaning survival. This could be also explained by several other environmental factors during the farrowing process. Fix et al. (2010b) also found parity to have a significant effect on birth weight.

Overall, progeny performance was also significantly affected by the dam's parity (Tables 2 and 3). Pigs farrowed by parity 1 dams were fatter and lighter muscled than pigs farrowed by parity 2 through parity 6 dams. Pigs farrowed by parity 1 dams also took significantly longer to reach 250 pounds than progeny of parity 2 through PG 7 dams. Pigs farrowed by parity 1 dams have lighter birth weights, which have generally been associated with poorer performance through market. Others have suggested that pigs that are farrowed by parity 1 dams also have reduced immunity levels which make them more susceptible to disease which can negatively affect performance (Declerck et al. 2016). The difference in performance and health status of these pigs has

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been the foundation for parity segregation. However, logistics of parity segregation are not always possible thus increasing the benefits of retaining mature sows in the herd when possible.

CONCLUSION

The results from the present study indicated that there is a significant drop in reproductive performance, progeny performance, and survivability of progeny between parity 1 sows and mature sows (parity 3 -7) that are retained in the herd. A gilt generally needs to produce at least three litters before she has out produced her initial cost, but replacement rates have steadily remained around 50 % on an annual basis. Though culling is inevitable, and gilts must be introduced into a sow herd, a herd turnover of 50% per year could significantly reduce a system's production. Voluntarily culling sows prior to parity 5 or 6 limits the productivity of the system by culling sows prior to reaching peak performance and replacing them with gilts that have significantly poorer reproductive performance, reduced progeny performance, and progeny with reduced odds of surviving to market.

Results also indicate that low birth weight piglets and litters from older parity sows have greater pre-weaning mortality and reduce the odds of survival until weaning. As the pressure for larger litters and optimum sow lifetime production increases, it is important for producers to use a balanced approach to selection objectives and realize the economic importance of culling sows at the appropriate time to replace her with a more productive and efficient female. Even though this study found statistical differences in number born alive and pre-wean mortality between parities, from a production standpoint the effects were minimal compared to the affect individual piglet birth weight. More emphasis needs to be placed on individual piglet birth weight and ways to reduce the total number of low birth weight piglets. More research needs to be done on how to deal with these piglets to improve pre-wean mortality.

Despite the fact that gilts and primiparous sows have significantly reduced reproductive performance compared to multiparous sows, there is little evidence of any substantial differences in the physiology of the reproductive process between these parity groups. This may be due to a lack of experiments designed to specifically examine the effects of age and parity on reproductive processes. Conversely, the increase in reproductive performance from gilts through the first few parities may be due in part to the removal of sub-fertile females from the breeding herd and not to some physiological change. Primiparous sows have lower lactation feed intake, longer wean-to-estrus intervals, an increased incidence of anestrus, and decreased FR and litter size compared to multiparous sows. Parity 1, and to some extent, P2 sows, are more susceptible to increased wean-to-estrus intervals and decreased farrowing rates than P3 or higher-parity sows after short lactation lengths.

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Table 1. Reproductive and Progeny Performance of Maternal Line Yorkshire Sows

Item	Mean \pm Standard Deviation	Standard	Minimum	Maximum
Farrowing, %	83.7	21.5	33.3	100.0
Number Born	12.8	3.3	3.0	18.0
Number Born Alive	10.7	2.9	2.0	16.0
Number Weaned	8.8	2.0	3.0	14.0
Birth Weight, kg	1.5	0.3	0.7	2.4
Weaning Weight, kg	8.4	1.6	3.2	11.3
Number Nursed After Transfer	10.4	2.2	4.0	15.0
Backfat Pre-Farrowing, mm	17.9	2.0	12.0	26.0
Backfat Post-Weaning, mm	14.2	1.5	10.0	19.0
Pre-Farrowing Weight, kg	269.1	33.7	181.4	323.0
Post-Weaning Weight, kg	230.2	35.0	140.6	292.1

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Table 2. Parity and Reproductive and Progeny Performance of Maternal Line Yorkshire Sows (Means ± Standard Deviation)

Item	Parity							
	1(n=24)	2 (n=24)	3 (n=14)	4 (n=12)	5 (n=10)	6 (n=6)	7 (n=5)	8+ (n=8)
Farrowing, %	72.61±28.95	85.40±20.79	93.75±12.50	85.83±9.58	95.83±8.35	81.80±25.74	87.50±0.00	94.40±6.47
Number Born	11.46±3.04	12.46±3.45	15.57±2.10	14.92±2.94	13.40±3.03	11.67±1.37	11.40±4.39	10.25±2.55
Number Born Alive	9.50±2.36	10.92±3.61	12.29±1.59	12.58±2.71	11.30±2.79	10.67±1.37	9.00±3.08	8.75±2.31
Number Weaned	8.33±2.06	8.79±2.38	9.64±1.45	9.75±1.86	8.80±2.04	8.67±1.86	8.80±0.84	7.38±1.60
Birth Weight, kg	1.53±0.32	1.55±0.27	1.57±0.16	1.48±0.31	1.48±0.20	1.50±0.25	1.78±0.48	1.62±0.18
Weaning Weight, kg	8.12±1.79	8.71±1.56	8.03±1.84	7.98±1.30	8.29±1.43	8.93±1.73	9.18±1.64	8.34±1.53
Number Nursed After Transfer	9.25±1.65	10.13±2.66	11.64±1.34	11.33±2.99	11.00±2.36	11.00±1.10	10.80±1.30	10.13±1.25
Backfat Pre-Farrowing, mm	19.17±2.16	17.54±2.02	17.50±1.74	17.25±1.42	18.40±1.90	16.67±2.16	17.40±1.95	17.87±2.01
Backfat Post-Weaning, mm	14.21±1.84	14.17±1.97	14.00±1.24	14.17±1.19	14.40±0.84	14.67±1.03	14.60±0.07	14.38±0.74
Pre-Farrowing Weight, kg	230.01±25.24	262.04±31.62	287.06±19.83	288.33±22.84	291.70±16.81	288.48±12.78	296.10±17.63	286.95±18.06
Post-Weaning Weight, kg	192.73±34.65	220.45±29.28	239.30±21.54	246.98±17.37	257.88±17.44	250.78±14.28	262.18±12.36	260.19±35.00

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Table 3. Effects of Sow Parity on Reproductive and Progeny Performance (*P*- values)

Items	P-Values	Significant*
Farrowing, % vs. Parity	0.4436	NS
Number Born vs. Parity	0.0003	**
Number Born Alive vs. Parity	0.0048	**
Number Weaned vs. Parity	0.1567	NS
Birth Weight, kg vs. Parity	0.5499	NS
Weaning Weight, kg vs. Parity	0.6744	NS
Number Nursed After Transfer vs. Parity	0.0298	*
Backfat Pre-Farrowing, mm vs. Parity	0.0168	*
Backfat Post-Weaning, mm vs. Parity	0.9884	NS
Pre-Farrowing Weight, kg vs. Parity	0.0000	**
Post-Weaning Weight, kg vs. Parity	0.0000	**

***Significant if ($P < 0.05$); ** Highly Significant if ($P < 0.01$); NS = Not significant**